

Physiological Response to Heat Stress and its Nutritional Management in Dairy Animals

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Abstract

As global warming progresses, animals experience heat stress more frequently and for longer periods of time, resulting in mortality and severe economic loss. Animals strive to regulate their body temperature through behavioral and physiological responses that increase heat loss and decreasing heat generation. Heat stress in animals can be reduced by physically altering the environment, developing of less sensitive breeds and improving nutritional management strategies that use dietary water, protein, fat, micronutrients and feed additives. This article covers how the bodies of dairy animals react to heat stress and how different diets might help to alleviate the problem.

Keywords: Animals, Dairy, Heat stress, Nutritional management

Introduction

Heat stress in animals is a major issue all around the world and significantly reduces milk production in dairy cattle. Modern dairy farming operations have increased internal heat loads due to the higher amount of milk production and rising environmental temperature and humidity. The temperature and humidity are the strongest predictor of heat stress in tropical regions. Heat stress symptoms include decreased rumination, growth, feed intake, fertility and carcass quality. Animals activate various adaptation such as increased sweating, respiration rate, decreased milk supply, vasodilation and decrease reproductive efficiency to combat the additional heat. There are various

strategies for reducing heat stress such as enhanced nutritional management including dietary water, fat, fiber, micronutrients and feed additives.

Impact of heat stress on animals

Heat stress causes an increase in sweating, water intake and reduced feed intake and heart rate. Heat acclimatization is accomplished through homeostatic processes when the heat load is raised. However, if heat stress persists, the animal may undertake homeostatic mechanisms to disperse increment in heat load and acclimate to stress circumstances. When the hypothalamus detects a temperature higher than the thermoneutral zone, heat loss mechanism such as perspiration and vasodilation are triggered. Animals during heat stress ingest a smaller amount of feed and ruminate less as a result, which reduces the quantity of buffering substances that reach the rumen. Additionally, blood flow is redirected to the periphery in an effort to improve heat degeneracy that causes a drop in flow of blood to the digestive tract and interferes with digestion.

Nutrients and feeding management

Water intake

The intake of dry matter is connected to the intake of water, which is controlled by both feed intake and feed type. Intake of water is affected by the water volume absorbed during eating, drinking and metabolic process, as well as the loss of water during sweating, lactation and respiration. During summer time water consumption is related to increased urine volume and evaporative heat loss, which is mostly caused by sweating. As a result, an adequate water supply for the animals under heat stress should be ensured.

Dietary fiber

Heat-stressed animals have lower energy usage efficiency. Diets high in fiber may increase heat output. Acetate metabolism generates extra endogenous heat as compared to propionate metabolism. Ruminant fed low fiber diets in warm weather had better daily milk output and lower respiratory rates than those fed high fiber diets. Following that, intake has a significant impact on heat generation, and its significance in developing an effective nutritional managing programme must be carefully considered. In lactating dairy animals, reducing NDF content from roughage reduced symptoms of heat stress, while improving dry matter intake and production of milk. Dietary fiber, on the other hand, is essential for normal rumen activity and supply. It is

hypothesized that eating easily fermentable grains to dairy animals throughout the summer would lower the heat production from fermentation and digestion process, hence improving physiological responses to heat stress and increasing productivity.

Dietary protein

The metabolic consumption of crude proteins increases endogenous heat output, which is larger than that of carbohydrates or fat. Urea production and higher protein turnover are both linked to a higher heat increment from crude proteins. During stress the quality of the protein source, as well as the amount of protein delivered, should be considered. Dietary essential amino acids may aid to lower the risk of heat stress. Heat stress affects RNA translational process, lowering milk protein synthesis. Methionine is an essential limiting amino acid in dairy animals. Supplementation of methionine increases production of milk and antioxidant activity while decreasing apoptosis of lymphocyte. Lysine was also found to be beneficial during heat stress conditions. However, given an adequate energy supply, it is critical to improve the quality of proteins by raising the level of important amino acids.

Dietary fat

In comparison to fiber or starch, supplementation of fat enhances net energy intake in stressed dairy animals. Dairy animal's diets supplemented with protected tallow used metabolizable energy more efficiently for lactation under thermo-neutral conditions than those not getting additional tallow. In a recent study, addition of unprotected fat (3%) was recommended for usage during the hot summer months. Higher circulatory NEFA concentrations were found in heat-stressed dairy cows fed a higher calorie diet, indicating a reduction in the energy deficit. As a result, yield of milk improved dramatically (28.50-30.40 kg/day), but content of milk fat decreased. Unprotected fat supplementation is thought to have disrupted fermentation process in ruminants, lowering acetate and propionate ratio and thus milk fat synthesis. Rumen-protected fats in diet considerably reduce metabolic heat, improve the lipid's role throughout the heat-stress phase. Using treated fat that bypasses the rumen atmosphere intact and so does not affect the rumen microorganisms, is clearly the best alternative.

Dietary micro nutrients

Adding mineral supplements to the diet (DCAD, Zinc, Chromium, Selenium, and so on) may help to lessen the harmful properties of thermal stress. Vitamins operate as cofactors for enzymes, act as catalysts different metabolic pathways, necessary for animal development.

Supplementing the feed of dairy animals with vitamins (Vitamin E, Niacin, etc.) may also aid to lessen the detrimental effects of heat stress (Singh, 2021; Singh et al., 2020a; Singh et al., 2020b). Studies have shown that the dietary cation-anion difference at a healthy lactating level remains a good strategy for reducing thermal stress during the warm summer months and improved the immunity status and nutrient intake. Zinc plays a critical role in anti-oxidant defense which is vital part of superoxide dismutase. The deficiency of zinc has been reported to cause an increase in oxidative DNA damage and impair antioxidant functions. Zinc supplementation lessens the heat shock protein response and enhances immunity in dairy animals.

Chromium is another favorable micronutrient to defy the harmful effects of heat stress in animals. It functions as a powerful antioxidant to stop lipid peroxidation during heat stress. Cortisol hormone and food metabolism are both enhanced by chromium. It increases insulin action in sensitive tissues, boosting the output of agricultural animals. Selenium lessens the adverse impact of stress on metabolism and redox equilibrium, which enhances the health, immunity and milk quality of dairy animals. It also dramatically increases plasma selenoprotein and selenium concentration, which may be potential method to protect dairy animals from heat stress.

Vitamin E is an antioxidant that is essential for body functions like growth, immunity, tissue integrity, reproduction, and preventing oxidative stress. Elevated temperature and humidity in summer will lead to greater oxidative stress for animals, so feeding of additional vitamin E is required. The role of tocopherol in inhibition of chronic disease thought to be related to oxidative stress has been extensively examined and positive results. Niacin is a vitamin that protects dairy animals from heat stress by boosting evaporative heat loss by raising heat shock protein gene expression under in vitro conditions. A study conducted at NDRI showed that 800 ppm niacin supplementation to lactating crossbred cattle resulted in better heat stress alleviation.

Feed additives

Yeast supplementation (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) improved feed efficiency, dry matter intake and lactation performance in dairy animals under heat stress. The addition of a combination of yeast culture and exogenous enzymes to heat-stressed dairy animals lowered rectal temperature, suggesting a role for thermoregulatory functions. *Aspergillus oryzae* was found to reduce the rectal temperature of heat-stressed animals. Due to an increase in glutathione peroxidase plasma activity, daidzein was considered to be a good promoter of antioxidants in stresses lactation cows. *Radix*

bupleuri extract (0.25 g/kg DM) showed antipyretic benefits in heat-stressed nursing dairy animals by dropping rectal temperature, and improving feed efficiency.

Conclusion

Heat stress is becoming a severe issue to its negative impact on ruminant performance. Nutritionists should consider changes in nutrient partitioning as well as adjustment to the rumen and intestinal functionality when developing diets during stress condition. Continued advancements in feeding are required because dairy animals are selected for high milk production. Creating nutritional plans that support milk production while also addressing the physiological and metabolic changes by heat stress will aid dairy animals in maintaining a more normal metabolism, which should improve animal performance.

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